

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF ENGLISH IN MEDICINE FOR UZBEK SPEAKERS.

TERMS OF CHILDREN'S DISEASES IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

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Abstract. *There are many reasons to study English for people working in the medical field. The first one is that most modern scientific literature is published in English. It is obvious that some essential details of the article may be lost in the process of translation, so if a person is competent in English, he can avoid the associated difficulties. Moreover, a medical professional can publish an article in English himself, thereby presenting the results of his research to the international medical community. Moreover, knowledge of the English language provides a number of opportunities for internships in English-speaking countries and international communication. Finally, the study of languages contributes to the development of memory, which is also necessary when studying medical disciplines.*

Keywords: *foreign languages, English in medicine, language learning.*

In the modern world, when it has become easier to travel abroad, knowledge of English is becoming more and more necessary [1]. According to statistics, English is the most commonly used foreign language. There are about 400 million native English speakers in the world and about 600-700 million people who use English as a foreign language. Thus, more than a billion people can at least somehow explain themselves in English. Although Chinese is the mother tongue of more people than English, grammar and writing are extremely difficult for those wishing to learn Chinese.

Latin is not used in colloquial speech, so this language is not actively developing and cannot fully meet the communicative needs of modern healthcare workers. Since more than half of the world's scientific journals are written in English, English can be recognized as the language of world medicine. Despite this, the level of English language proficiency in Uzbekistan is rather low among all segments of the population, including among healthcare workers. Sometimes even English teachers in schools and universities have gaps in English knowledge and do not have developed communication skills.

This often leads to the fact that people who study English cannot master the language at a good level and therefore feel insecure, afraid of making a mistake in the process of learning English. Unfortunately, most medical students are not ready to learn medical English because they have not mastered the basic grammar and vocabulary of the English language in school. Learning specific medical vocabulary is as pointless without a basic command of the language as trying to build a house without a foundation. In order to confirm this assumption, I interviewed 90 students and employees of TFTMA (85 students and 5 employees). First of all, the respondents were asked to rate their current level of English, according to the Common Standards (CEFR) [2].

Research shows the levels of English proficiency of TBTMA students and staff. In general, the level of English among the respondents is low. About 60% of the respondents speak a foreign language at the A1-A2 level, about 40 at the B1-B2 level, and only a small number of medical

students have an advanced level of English. However, the majority of respondents argue that knowledge of the English language is necessary for the successful work of the future physician. As a result of the survey, a general trend was revealed: with experience in medicine, employees acquire an understanding that English is needed in the medical profession.

Undoubtedly, there are many reasons why English is essential for healthcare professionals. Firstly, most modern medical articles are written in English, so knowing English allows you to access the latest scientific developments.

As you know, in the process of translation, some details can be lost, so if a student or doctor knows a foreign language, they can use the text in the original, thus avoiding potential loss of information. In addition, English proficiency increases the ability of health workers to collaborate internationally. If a doctor understands English, then he can explain his ideas and conduct his research with colleagues from other countries, thus establishing international scientific contacts. Being able to speak English can give you more job opportunities, such as working with international patients or medical students. At the same time, the salary of a medical worker will be significantly higher.

Doctors who speak English professionally have more employment opportunities as they can train abroad or stay in an English-speaking country as a medical professional or scientist. Generally, in English-speaking countries, a doctor can access the latest equipment and a better quality of life in general. Conducting research at a high level will make it possible to describe the results achieved in medical journals recognized by the world community, and this will allow scientists to receive an international vocation. Language learning has also been shown to be beneficial for memory training, which is a necessary skill not only for personal growth but also for the study of medicine. The vast majority of respondents are not currently learning languages on their own. The exception is students of secondary vocational education (nursing), because English lessons, in which work is done on the translation of texts and the study of medical terminology, are included in their curriculum.

However, apart from these compulsory classes and homework, SVE students do not study foreign languages. The main reasons why students and health care workers do not learn English are overload with educational and work tasks, lack of time and lack of the ability to effectively allocate available time, lack of money to pay for foreign language tutors. People who learn a language on their own have a higher level of language competence. Although the requirements for university students are high, they can improve their English in their free time by watching movies or reading books, as well as chatting with people via Skype or other platforms in real time.

Another problem is that people learning a new language often focus on passive (or perceptual) skills like reading and listening, but many don't pay attention to active skills like speaking and writing. This correlates with the results of the survey: 41% of respondents said that English is necessary for reading articles, but only 8% took into account that they can write articles themselves and communicate with the global medical community. Most of the respondents expressed the opinion that in order to improve their language level, they should focus on learning new words, reading, doing grammar exercises and watching videos.

Only a few respondents stated that the practice of speaking English is important. To this end, you can find an English-speaking partner to practice on Skype, attend conversation clubs, or move to an English-speaking country. In real life, one should not always strive to master a foreign

language at a high level. For example, for successful work in medical laboratories with rare communication with people, learning spoken English will not be particularly useful.

Summing up, it must be said that the situation with the study of English in Uzbekistan is not without difficulties, since there is not enough motivation among the population for independent study of languages. A significant obstacle is also the lack of professional English teachers in Russia, especially at the school level. However, the exchange of information and the introduction of a communicative approach to the study of foreign languages are potentially good incentives to improve the situation.

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